

Trends and cycles in indexed equities

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Historical daily-price data has been obtained (for a fee) from macrotrends.dpdcart.com.

The chart below displays the DJIA from Dec-1914 to Jan-2022 on logarithmic scales; conventional on the upper tier and triple-log ($\log(\log(\log(*)))$) on the lower, just to emphasize the disastrous price drop that began at the end of 1929, taking some twenty-five years for recovery.

The debacle looks even worse for the S&P index; see below, using the same logarithmic scales.

The following OCTAVE computations were performed on both sets to discover cyclic behavior:

- a) Generate a cumulative sum on the logarithm of each set: `cumsum(log(*))`
- b) Estimate a curve-fit to the result with a 3rd order polynomial: `polyval(polyfit)` commands
- c) Obtain the residual difference: `polyval(polyfit)` minus `cumsum(log(*))`
- d) Take the sign of the residual to more readily exhibit periodicity

Tiered & labeled results for the DJIA index follow immediately below, showing long-term cyclicality.

Next, S&P results, showing similar, though not identical, behavior.

In both cases a negative residual period matched an index decline or relative stagnation, while a positive period augured an index rise. It is noteworthy that the DJIA residual first became negative in **July of 1927**, well before the well-known catastrophic events.

DJIA index cycles

Above, the residual chart for the DJIA clearly shows five complete, alternating cycles; the list below dates the onsets – up (U) and down (D) – and the index beginning value underneath.

Jul-1927 (D)	Sep-1942 (U)	Jun-1963 (D)	Jun-1982 (U)	Dec-1999 (D)	Jun-2015 (U)
177.02	106.34	723.36	816.51	11484.70	18039.40

The multi-tiered chart below shows the historic behavior of each cycle; the term ‘range’ refers to index endpoint difference (last minus first).

Thus the **negative residual** intervals durations (in years) and endpoint index differences were:

[15.13	18.98	15.45]
[-70.68	93.15	6554.7]

for an average of **16.52 yrs.** Similarly, **positive residual** interval durations and index ranges were:

[20.77	17.57]
[617.02	10668.2]

for an average of **19.17 yrs.** Overall cycle average was **17.58 yrs.**

The DJIA appears currently to be in growth mode; using just the average interval of 17.58 yrs., this long-term trend which began mid-2015 should continue through **2033**.

S&P index cycles

Similar, though not identical, results hold for the S&P index; the list below dates the onsets and the index beginning values

Dec-1930 (D)	Feb-1945 (U)	Jul-1963 (D)	Nov-1980 (U)	Jul-1999 (D)	May-2014 (U)
5.43	13.51	69.76	139.33	1394.42	1878.33

The multi-tiered chart below shows the historic behavior of each cycle for this index.

This time the **downward** interval durations were:

[14.14 17.38 14.81]

or **15.44 yrs.** on average.

Upward interval durations were:

[18.44. 18.61]

and an average of **18.53 yrs.** Overall interval average here is **15.68 yrs**; the current upward trend for the S&P index long-term trend should continue into the next decade.

Thus both indexes appear to be in growth mode for considerably many more years.

Finally, these methods may be used to discover short-term trend changes across local data spans. For example, for the DJIA index from 1920 to 1940, the chart below shows the index in logarithmic scale (in blue); the sign of the upshifted residual - overlaid in black - indicates the onset dates of trend reversals.

Similarly, for the shorter and more recent period 2012-2022, the image below shows the corresponding local reversals; the signed residual has been scaled and shifted for the overlay.

For the even shorter period 2019-2021 trend reversal indicators are still evident; see below.

